

ANALYSIS OF ADULT TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENTS' SALIVARY PROFILES IN BABYLON PROVINCE

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Abstract

Background: There has not been much agreement on the hypothesis that diabetes is associated with salivary dysfunction, thus we looked at salivary parameters in diabetic and non-diabetic people. Diabetes mellitus may be diagnosed and monitored more effectively if saliva is used instead of blood. **Materials and Methods:** At least two years before the start of the trial, all participants had been diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes mellitus in one form or another and were on antidiabetic therapy. All of the saliva was collected in a fasting state without any stimulus. Measurements of saliva's organic and inorganic content, pH, flow rate, and other parameters were made. These findings were then put under statistical scrutiny. **Results:** Salivary pH, flow rate and salivary amylase were significantly lower in diabetics who were on antidiabetic therapy. They had significantly higher levels of salivary glucose, total proteins, sodium and potassium and lower levels of calcium in comparison to those in the non-diabetic group. **Conclusion:** Diabetics and non-diabetics differed significantly in the physical and biochemical properties of their saliva. It is possible to screen, diagnose, and monitor for diabetes using salivary characteristics, which are less intrusive than blood tests.

Keywords: Adult Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus ; Salivary Profiles ; blood tests; Babylon Province

Introduction

Although Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) may be treated, long-term complications remain the biggest health dangers. Worldwide and in Babylon city, epidemiological research reveal that the burden of T2DM is increasing significantly. Per J E Shaw et al., diabetes will affect 7.7 percent of individuals (20–79 years old) by 2030 [1]. There are no exceptions to this pattern in our country. With increasing rates of obesity, type 2 diabetes (T2DM) and cardiovascular disease (CVD) mortality and morbidity in the United States are on the rise[2,3], There are several organ systems that are affected by diabetes mellitus (DM). It is possible for people with diabetes mellitus type 2 (T2DM) to develop neuropathy and other neuropathy-related conditions due to long-term high blood sugar levels[4].

Furthermore, salivary glands seem to be affected. Xerostomia, periodontitis, gingivitis, odontogenic abscesses, and soft tissue lesions of the tongue and oral mucosa are among the documented oral health concerns associated with T2DM that practitioners often observe[5]. As a result of poorly controlled Type 2 Diabetes, salivary function suffers. Autonomic neuropathies, microvascular alterations, hormonal abnormalities, or a combination of these might cause

diabetics to have salivary hypofunction and dehydration[6].

T2DM and salivary dysfunction in diabetes have yet to be established as a plausible link between the two conditions. This research was designed to test the hypothesis that physical and biochemical properties of saliva differ between diabetes and nondiabetic patients. Flow rates, morphological properties, and biochemical profiles of participants' saliva were studied, as was the association between fasting plasma glucose levels and salivary parameters, in this study, which included participants with and without diabetes.

Materials and Methods

This research included 30 diabetics and 30 non-diabetics. People were chosen at random from a pool of prospective volunteers (Table 1). Diabetes had been diagnosed at least two years before to participating in this study, and all participants were undergoing antidiabetic therapy at a private hospital. Participants ranged in age from 40 to 55. As early as the first year after diagnosis, it has been shown that DM difficulties begin to develop. T2DM had been present in the lives of the participants for at least two years. In order to exclude participants with depression, edentulism, or systemic illness, the researchers eliminated individuals with radiation to the head and neck[7-9].

Table 1.

Participants age group			
Patients age group	No.	Healthy age group	No.
40-45	14	40-45	12
45-50	7	45-50	10
50-55	9	50-55	8
Total	30	Total	30

People who were not diabetic but had gone to the emergency department or lab for another test made up the control group. This study required all participants to complete a written informed consent form before they were allowed to participate in it.

At 7 to 8 a.m. in the morning, while they were fasting, researchers administered demographic and medical questionnaires to the participants, after which samples of saliva were taken from them. For five minutes, we

collected unstimulated entire saliva using a standardized spitting method. To ensure that there was no selection bias, all of the individuals' saliva was collected by a single observer. Glass electrodes from Systronics' pH system were used to test the salivary pH in less than an hour after the samples had been collected from the subjects.

Calculated salivary flow rates were represented as millilitres per minute (ml/min).

At 5000 rpm, the samples were centrifuged, and the supernatant was collected and kept at -8C until further analysis was possible. There was also a look at the biochemical features of the saliva. Inorganic elements such as sodium and calcium were present together with organic substances such as glucose and total protein (analysed by using a semi auto analyzer). SPSS version 15 was used to do the statistical evaluation. A Student's t-test was used to compare the salivary parameters between diabetics and those without diabetes.

Results and Discussion

We recruited a total of sixty participants, 30 of whom had diabetes and were on antidiabetic therapy and 30 of whom had normal blood sugar levels. Participant average was 48.7 years. It was reported that there

were 30 diabetics in all, with a median age of 49.11 years for the 12 men and 18 females. Average age for the non-diabetic individuals was 44.44 years; 14 men and 16 women were in excellent health at that age. A comparison of pH, salivary flow rates, and biochemical markers in the male and female groups revealed no differences.

In Table 2, we display the mean standard deviation for salivary pH and entire salivary flow rate at rest in non-diabetics and diabetics. In diabetics, salivary pH levels were much lower than in individuals without diabetes. (Non Diabetics (ND) $=8.11 \pm 0.17$, Diabetics (D) $=5.83 \pm 0.05$, $p=0.000$). The flow rate in diabetics was considerably reduced with values of 0.38 ± 0.22 and in ND it was 0.61 ± 0.17 which was statistically significant ($p=0.002$). Non-diabetics and diabetics differed significantly in their biochemical profiles [Table 3]. Diabetics had higher amounts of salivary glucose, total protein, sodium, and potassium, as well as lower levels of calcium ($p=0.0001$). Among diabetics, there was a statistically significant drop in salivary amylase concentrations ($p=0.0001$).

Table 2.

The mean standard deviation for salivary pH and entire salivary flow rate at rest in non-diabetics and diabetics

"Parameter Studied"	Non Diabetic Subjects (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	Diabetic Subjects (MEAN $\pm$ SD)	p value
Salivary pH	8.11 ± 0.17	$5.83 \pm 0.05^*$	$p=0.000$
Salivary flow rate(ml/min)	0.61 ± 0.17	$0.38 \pm 0.22^*$	$p=0.002$

Table 3.

Biochemical profiles of the saliva in non-diabetics and diabetics

Parameter Studied	Non-Diabetic Subjects (Mean $\pm$ Sd)	Diabetic Subjects (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p Value
Glucose (mg/dl)	3.27 ± 0.17	$19.55 \pm 1.55^*$	$p=0.001$
Salivary alpha amylase	103.51 ± 08.55	$15.88 \pm 1.6^*$	$p=0.0001$
Total proteins(g/l)	466.38 ± 186.33	$856.19 \pm 403.67^*$	$p=0.001$
Sodium(mEq/l)	3.89 ± 0.36	$16.52 \pm 0.98^*$	$p=0.001$
Potassium(mEq/l)	22.12 ± 0.67	$28.77 \pm 0.22^*$	$p=0.001$
Calcium(mEq/l)	7.08 ± 0.22	$3.66 \pm 0.08^*$	$p=0.0001$

Drugs such as anticholinergic and diuretics, anti-histamines, anti-hypertensives, etc., may modify salivary parameters in people with metabolic and neurological problems as well as those who are dehydrated [10]. Salivary secretions may be altered by diabetes-related microvascular issues and, as a result, autonomic neuropathy [11]. Although several research have been undertaken to examine the effects of T2DM on salivary functioning, the results are still ambiguous. Because of this, we decided to conduct our research on a diabetic population from Babylon City in order to see whether the physical and biochemical properties of saliva in diabetics differ from those of non-diabetic controls. The idea was to suggest that saliva may replace blood in the diagnosis and monitoring of diabetics.

Resting salivary pH in healthy people was estimated in many investigations to be between 5.5 and 7.9 [12]. The pH of saliva is maintained by buffers such as carbonic acid and bicarbonate systems, phosphate

systems, and protein systems [13]. Patients with diabetes have pH values that are lower than those of healthy individuals. Diabetic participants exhibited an acidic pH as well, which M E Lopez *et al.*, found to be caused by the presence of bacteria or by the drop in bicarbonate levels that occurred with the increase in flow rate [14]. However, there is a lack of research on salivary pH alterations in T2DM.

In the absence of external stimulation, the mouth produces a combination of secretions known as resting saliva. For those who suffer from dry mouth and hyposalivation, the flow rate is substantially below the normal 0.3-0.5 ml/min resting rate for entire saliva. Citric acid is known to cause an increase in saliva flow rate between 1.0 and 3.0 ml/min. In diabetics, the salivary flow rate is much lower than in the general population. Those with diabetes have been shown to have a decreased salivary flow rate than those without diabetes.

Due to an increased diuresis caused by inadequate glycaemic control, diabetics have increased thirst and dry mouth. People with and without type II diabetes who were studied by Cherry–Peppers et al. for flow rate came to the same conclusion[15-17].

Those with Type 1 diabetes were shown to have lower salivary flow rates than those with normal glycaemic control and those who were not diabetic. When blood glucose levels are under control, it seems that normal salivary flow rates may be restored[10,18]. Moreover Sugary saliva production, which is controlled by the autonomic nerve system, may be a symptom of diabetes autonomic neuropathy in diabetic individuals. Studies by Meurman and Tenovuo found no difference in salivary secretion rates between T2DM patients and healthy controls[19,20].

The levels of glucose in the saliva of diabetics were found to be much greater than those of healthy people. One possible explanation for this is that glucose homeostasis has changed. Blood glucose filters, according to Chatterton RT and colleagues[21], may be influenced by hormonal or neurological regulation of the salivary glands[22]. Another study found that diabetics have higher salivary glucose levels than non-diabetics. It was shown that diabetics' salivary glucose levels had a negative correlation with their glycaemic status, as well as their HbA1c levels, in another study by Lopez *et al.*, [12,13]. Karjalainen *et al.*, [16] found that once insulin therapy was began, diabetics' salivary glucose levels dropped. There was no difference in salivary glucose levels reported by Sharon *et al.*, [23]. Diabetics have lower levels of salivary amylase than non-diabetics. Streptozotocin-treated rats had lower levels of parotid gland amylase and amylase mRNA, but insulin therapy raised amylase levels prior to any change in mRNA levels[24], which was in agreement with our findings. This data suggests an early impact on protein translation and maybe a long-term transcriptional effect[25]. People with poorly controlled noninsulin-dependent diabetes who had increased amylase activity had changed taste sensations. Amylase levels in the saliva of diabetics have yet to be established as a reliable indicator. Diabetes patients' salivary amylase levels were found to be significantly greater than those of the controls, as reported by Yavuzilmaz et al. and by Chatterton RT et al. In the research by J. Tenovuo *et al.*, [26], no variations were seen in the amylase activity across the study groups.

The findings of this investigation indicated that diabetics had considerably higher amounts of salivary total proteins. Microorganism activity or periodontal tissue-derived proteins may be to blame for a rise in salivary protein levels. Exocrine gland proteins may be more likely to enter secretions in people with diabetes if the basement membrane is more permeable, according to Mandel's hypothesis[10]. Even while diabetics' salivary protein concentrations have been reported to be greater than those of non-diabetics in certain investigations, this has not been the case in other studies. Proteins released from gingival fluid rather than saliva have been associated to high levels of active periodontal disease in diabetics, according to research[4].

Sodium and potassium levels in diabetics were greatly high, whereas calcium levels were dramatically lowered, according to the findings of our research. T2DM and IDDM (Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus) patients had considerably higher potassium levels in their saliva than healthy controls, too[4]. As a result of either hyperaldosteronism or a decreased Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase function, diabetic individuals may have abnormally high potassium levels in their salivary glands. Harrison *et al.*, [27] found that potassium levels were in agreement, however calcium levels were in disagreement.

Researchers have looked at the possibility of using saliva instead of plasma to diagnose or monitor type 2 diabetes by evaluating the extent of changes in saliva's composition. Cellular and chemical studies of blood components are the most frequently utilized laboratory diagnostic methods. When it comes to fluids in our bodies, saliva has several unique benefits over other fluids. An examination of salivary gland secretions is a primary tool for determining the particular disease of the glands, such as infection and blockage.

The most common use of a salivary analysis for the assessment of systemic illnesses is the study of entire saliva. In certain cases, systemic illnesses impact the salivary glands in such a way that they not only change the amount of saliva produced, but also its makeup. Like T2DM, these disorders may be diagnosed and detected earlier if they have a distinctive set of symptoms. Because of its simplicity, reliability, and lack of harm, saliva has lately been utilized to make diagnoses for a broad variety of disorders[10].

Individuals with little training may collect whole saliva non-invasively. For its collection, there is no need for any particular equipment. Children and the elderly may benefit from saliva testing for illness diagnosis since saliva collection is linked with less compliance issues than blood collection. In addition, salivary analysis seems to be a cost-effective strategy for screening huge groups of people.

Because of the limited sample size, we were unable to draw any firm conclusions on the changes in salivary parameters that occur in diabetics in this research. Fasting plasma glucose levels were linked to a variety of salivary indicators, including glucose, although a larger sample size would have allowed us to draw more certain conclusions. In addition, analysing the HbA1c levels of the participants' glycaemic controls would have added value.

Acknowledgments: I'm extremely grateful to nurses, laboratories staff and participants.

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